

ISSN 2181-8622

Manufacturing technology problems

**Scientific and Technical Journal
Namangan Institute of
Engineering and Technology**

**Volume 8
Issue 1
2023**

GREEN ECONOMY AND GREEN GROWTH. INITIAL EFFORTS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKSITAN

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Abstract: Green economy and green growth play a key role in the transformation to the sustainable development from traditional development. In the world all nations are trying to change their traditional economy to the sustainable economic development in the form of green economy and green growth.

In this paper, we have taken mostly into consideration all fields of green economy such as creating energy efficiency policies, enhancing to produce green product and increase the consumption of green products, promoting green jobs, upgrading environmental and socioeconomic impacts of the country's latest green economy policies and green growth strategies for the upcoming years. We have tried to demonstrate profitable sides of the long term sustainable development rather than short term benefits of the new policies.

Keywords: Green economy, green growth, sustainable development, socioeconomic, green economy policy, green growth strategies, climate change, natural resources, human wellbeing, traditional economy, renewable energy.

Introduction. The concept of green economy has been evolved since 1972 at the UN Conference on the Human Environment declaration "We have only one earth" [1]. But this idea green economy and green growth or sustainable development has been the core idea of the economy of all nations in the late on XX century and XXI century. We have seen the UNEP statistics, Green Economic Institution articles, High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development (HLPF) and Green Growth Knowledge Platform (GGKP) annual reports about the green economy and green growth. European countries have encountered green economy and green growth more deeply than other countries, cause more people who is living in these areas are wants to life safe, ecofriendly, fresh air places, even they want to buy the products that have been produced in the form of green products more expensive tant the goods that have been manufactured in the form of traditional economy.

Like other nations, Asian and central Asian countries also have given their great attention to the sustainable development. Korea, Japan, China and other well developed countries in Asia also have great experiences towards the sustainable

development. In Asia the most complex and crucial socio-economic phenomenon of the twenty first century is rapid urbanization and more scarce recurse than passed centuries. It represents significant irreversible changes in production and consumption and in the manner in which people interact with nature.

Our today's economy and our way of life today are based mainly on of fossil fuels, which not only threaten essential environmental and social problems through global warming in the entire world, Aral sea phenomenon in central Asia, at actual consumption rate, will run out within few decades, causing enormous industrial and economic disaster. Uzbeksitan is one part of many nations who is suffering these phenomenon (Aral sea disaster). Lots of efforts have been made to tackle this problem and in order to get long term sustainable development we should change our behavior towards the economy, step by step new rules and legislations have to be made to change traditional economy to the green economy and green growth. Finally, mankind understood that nature is one, resources are scarce but our behavior towards the nature is not good, even worse. Green economy is one that promotes economic opportunities that are

not conflict with environmental sustainability and social well-being. It also promotes environmental objectives that can provide new forms of social economic opportunities.

Green economy can be one tool that manages social equity, human well-being, with an improved economy while reducing ecological and environmental risks. This paper will give a general idea for green economy, green growth and sustainable development through international case studies that applied this concept to the cities of Uzbekistan and their environments. Finally, this paper will focus on new rules and legislation towards the green economy and sustainable development, by analyzing them give reliable recommendations to create better eco-friendly life in Uzbekistan.

Literature review. There is no literally accepted definition of the term “green economy” and “green growth”. The core idea of the “green economy” derived from the idea of UN Conference on the Human Environment “We have only one earth” [1], but the term “green economy” was first coined in a pioneering 1989 report for the Government of the United Kingdom by a group of leading environmental economists, entitled “Blueprint for a Green Economy” [2]. Although there are no exact priority concepts related to the green economy, a number of the EU’s headline and Asia’s headline priorities and sector specific strategies and policies could form part of the green economy transition.

Although the green economy has a legacy from “Limits to Growth arguments” [4] and the “Blueprint for a Green Economy” [3], currently iterations of the green economy entered mainstream policy

discourse towards the end of the 2000, for now it is notably main idea for all economists from the UNEP’s green economy reports.

The concept of a “green economy” does not replace sustainable development, but there is now a growing recognition that achieving sustainability rests almost entirely on getting the economy right. Decades of creating new wealth through a “brown economy” model have not substantially addressed social marginalization and resource depletion, and we are still far from delivering to the Millennium Development Goals. Sustainability is still a vital long-term goal, but we must work on greening the economy to get us there.

“Green economy” and “green growth” have many definitions which pay attention to different points. (See table 1). It is defined as a sustainable economy and society with a one-planet footprint where all energy is developed from the renewable resources. Green economy sectors include, for example clean technologies, improved freshwater infrastructure, sustainable energy, low carbon transport and energy efficient design, waste management clean technologies, sustainable agriculture energy and forestry. According to the UNEP (2011), a green economy is an economy caused by significantly reducing environmental risks through improved human welfare and social equity. In such sort of economy, all types of investments that reduce pollution and carbon emissions, improve resource and energy efficiency beside stop loss of biodiversity and footprint impacts are main elements affected income and employment.

Table 1.

Some green economy definitions

Source	Definition	Link
(UNEP)'s working definition, 2012	“Green economy” is an economy that results in improved human well-being and reduced inequalities over the long term, while not exposing future generations to significant environmental risks and ecological scarcities	UNEP 2012 annual report UNEP - UN Environment Programme
International Chamber of Commerce, Green Economy Task Force	The green economy is an economy in which economic growth and environmental sustainability work together in a mutually reinforcing fashion, while supporting progress and social development.	ICC’s new task force on Green Economy announces Chairperson - ICC - International Chamber of Commerce (iccwbo.org)
EEA (2013)	The green economy is one in which environmental, economic and social policies and innovations enable society to use resources efficiently—enhancing human well-being in an inclusive manner, while maintaining the natural systems that sustain us.	EEA 2013 Work Programme to Address Air Pollution, Climate Change, Energy News SDG Knowledge Hub IISD

Green economy and green growth are not the same thing, “green economy” was evaluated by the Europe meanwhile Asian countries like Korea, Japan, China, Indonesia came up with new idea “Green growth” at the beginning of the XXI century. At the “Fifth Ministerial Conference on Environment and Development” (MCED) [5] held in March 2005 in Seoul, 52 Governments and other stakeholders from Asia and the Pacific agreed to move beyond the sustainable development rhetoric and pursue a path of “green growth”. To do so, they adopted a Ministerial declaration (the Seoul Initiative Network on Green Growth) and a regional implementation plan for sustainable development. This commenced a broader vision of green growth as a regional initiative of UNESCAP, where it is viewed as a key strategy for achieving sustainable development as well as the Millennium

Development Goals (in particular 2 and 7 relating to poverty reduction and environmental sustainability) (UNESCAP, 2012).

There are many definitions to the “Green growth” but one of the important one is definition of OECD in 2011, “green growth means fostering economic growth and development while ensuring that natural assets continue to provide the resources and environmental services on which our well-being relies. To do this it must catalyse investment and innovation which will underpin sustained growth and give rise to new economic opportunities”

Classical growth theory assumes that output Q is produced using technology and human capital A, physical capital K, and labor L. The relationship among these inputs in the production, we can write in a mathematical way like this function:

$$Q = f(A, K, L) \text{ [6]}$$

In this formula we can demonstrate classical growth in production factors K and L, growth in productivity Q (quantity). Growth in labor L is explained by population growth, labor force participation and improvements in health and education. Growth in K is explained by investment, and growth models assume that a share of

output is used to increase the stock of capital K. Growth in A is explained by technological change, including changes in organization and practices, and by social capital improvement.

The environment becomes “natural capital”, directly needed for growth, and environmental management becomes a

productive investment, directly comparable to investment in physical capital. A failure to manage the environment results in the

depreciation and destruction of natural capital, with direct impacts on output. We thus have:

$$Q = f(A, K, L, E) \text{ [7]}$$

Here we can see E as environmental challenges. This demonstrates green growth rather than classical growth. All nations are trying to take into consideration environmental challenges in producing different products. As we know resources are limited, we should treat well towards the natural resources on earth.

Discussion. Global climate change threatens to disrupt the well-being of society, undermine economic development and alter the natural environment, making it a key policy concern of the 21st century. Climate change means a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods (UN, 1992). Climate change also has been damaged one part of our nation, Uzbekistan. One of the essential sea of the

central Asia is situated in Uzbekistan, Aral sea. Most parts of the Aral sea has been droughted by the nations which is situated in central Asia in the form of using incorrect way, so should try to safe our nature, our well-being, our economy. To do this we should support the idea of “Green economy”, “Green growth” and sustainable development.

Worldwide, all nations have their own prospective towards the green economy and green growth. But, green economy has some multiple proses in general, we can see them in the following table 2. They figure out that all thing should be green like green jobs, green technology, green tourism, green food, green products, green nature green building and green services and green structure. All these terms have already taken an action in Europe and supported in the form of RDPs (Rural Development Programmes).

Table 2.

Multiple benefits of green economy

Uzbekistan recognizes that moving a low-carbon emission is important for the

future prosperity and environmental sustainability. There are many rural areas

that are not being used, by understanding this we should create green places and green jobs by using these lands. To transform the economy of Uzbekistan into the new economic system by including the green growth, green economy and sustainable development inside the new economic system. By understanding these conditions President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev has signed decision "On the measures to increase the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to transition to a "green" economy by 2030" [8] to establish green economy, green growth and sustainable development. This decision includes many essential tasks that we have to tackle year by year in the late of 2030. The main issues indicated in this decision are the implementation of the tasks defined in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the "green" and inclusive economic transition within the framework of the strategy of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The work to be done in order to increase the effectiveness of the measures to ensure energy, use of renewable energy sources, and to further expand the saving of resources in all

sectors of the economy is consistently and clearly indicated. Problematic issues related to climate change have a negative impact on the effectiveness of reforms implemented in the country, in particular, on economic growth and poverty reduction, as well as ensuring environmental and food security. Based on this, in this direction, great attention is paid to reducing the impact of climate change and adapting to it, accelerating the transition to a "green" economy, and promoting a "green" and inclusive economic growth model. To increase the effectiveness of the measures taken on the development of the "green" economy based on the strategy of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period of 2019-2030, as well as the cooperation of state authorities and management bodies with international organizations in this direction. to ensure coordinated efforts in mutual cooperation created the need to develop a program. The following main goals and tasks are clearly defined in the green economy development program.

The program of transition to "green" economy and ensuring "green" growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 includes the following chapters.[10]

Graph 1.

The priorities defined in this program are based on a number of strategic directions in the fields that exist at the national level and strengthen their complementary aspects, for example technological modernization and introduction of "green" technologies, increasing literacy of the population in the field of "green" economy, supporting "green" investments from the foreign institutions, etc. The program defines the tasks of ensuring "green" economic growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the following graph 2.

Graph 2.

Six priorities of "Green" growth in Uzbekistan

Along with all countries, it is necessary for us to develop measures against climate change not only for our economic system, but also for improving external economic relations, improving the well-being of the population, and showing that we are a country that has its place economically in the world. The development of the green economy sector started with the decision of PQ-4477 dated October 5, 2019, adopted by our president, and the 26th session of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change held in November 2021 (COR26) within the framework of the Paris

Agreement, the Republic of Uzbekistan undertakes an additional obligation to reduce greenhouse gas emissions per unit of gross domestic product by 35 percent compared to 2010 levels by 2030 [11], we can mention this measure as a consistent continuation of activities in this field.

Conclusion. In 2019, President of Uzbekistan has signed an order related to the proposed green growth and green economy. From that time, we have been trying to change the economy in the good side, long term sustainable development. We should not forget that to establish green economy and green growth in one country

firstly, this country has to be ready this change. As knowing these conditions we set many tasks to tackle in the next decade. At present climate issues have gradually evolved into a focus of international political, social and economic competition. Whether green growth can be achieved could determine the outcomes of this competition. We are not part of this competition nowadays, but we will be main part of this competition in a few years. In Europe like Germany, Italy, Spain, UK and in Asia like Japan, Republic of Korea, China, Vietnam, Malisa countries' economies are mainly contain green economy and sustainable development. They have many concepts, action plans, priorities to get long term sustainable development.

We should not forget that everything have to be hard at the beginning. In order to get long term sustainable development, in some cases we should lose, we should not choose benefits of usual economy's short term benefits. On the one hand, green growth help achieve carbon reduction and sustainable development in the long run, on the other hand, it may force high-emission industries stop their operating. By studying and learning many scholar's articles, reports, publications and our president Sh. M. Mirziyoev's signed order, I have these recommendations in general.

Firstly, before turning into the green economy from traditional economy, we should give some illustrations about the green economy and its effects to the well-being, social life to the population its pros to the economy, cause most people nowadays want to live in developed cities or capital of the Uzbekistan but green economy mostly related to the RDPs (Rural Development Programs). So, if we want to enhance the green economy and green growth in Uzbekistan, we should create well social life in rural places, but now it is somehow costly for Uzbekistan.

Secondly, among our population there is no exact idea what is the green economy and green growth, we should broadcast information about the green economy in publicly.

Lastly, we should give grants to the scholars, who knows green economy better than others, to get more knowledge in this area in well developed countries like Germany, Italy, Korea, Indonesia and so on.

A limitation of this study is lack of analysis of industry-level data related to the green economy, as in Uzbekistan lack of organizations are producing green products. We use all information we have related to the green economy in Uzbekistan. In our follow-up study, additional studies will be done on specific industries, thus providing new insights.

References

1. Sh.M.Mirziyoev. "On the measures to increase the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to transition to a "green" economy by 2030". Uzbekistan. 2019.
2. UN Conference on the Human Environment declaration. Europe. "We have only one earth" 1972.
3. David W. Pearce. Blueprint for a Green Economy – Europe. 1989.
4. Deadows concepts. Limits to Growth arguments – Europe. 1972
5. Radoslava Kanianska. Green growth and green economy. Banská Bystrica. 2017-page 21.
6. Radoslava Kanianska. Green growth and green economy. Banská Bystrica. 2017-page 22.
7. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change held in (COR26). Europe. November 2021

8. Malin Song, Shuai Zhu, Jialian Wang, Jiajia Zhao. Share green growth. Regional evolution of green output performance in China. 2020
9. Mohammad Refaat Mohammad Abdelaal, Islam Sallam. Green economy themes. Pathway to sustainable urban development. 2019
10. Eu Rural Review. Green economy opportunities for rural Europe. Europe. 2017.
11. Adrian C. Newton and Elena Cantarello. An introduction to the green economy. London, New York. 2014.

Networks.

12. www.greeneconomics.org.uk
13. www.unep.org
14. www.enrd.ec.europa.eu
15. www.oecd.org

THE METHODS FOR MEASURING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP ACTIVITY

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Abstract:

Objectives: The main objective of this study is measuring capability of a wide range of social enterprises. The theoretical basis of the scale is supported by empirical research in the social sector. The scale provides a valid, reliable tool for measuring a wide range of SE in firms which meets different types of properties that required for measuring scales in the validity, social sciences or reliability.

Methods. Within the framework of the problem of measuring efficiency social entrepreneurship describes the most common and popular approaches and measurement methods forms and content achieved by social entrepreneurs the results of their activities. The most common problems of measuring and evaluating social outcomes and social effects faced by social entrepreneurs who firmly believe that indicators of accuracy and interpretation of results allow them to deepen your knowledge and understanding of the true situation organization and their real status in the community of social entrepreneurs.

Results. The results of this study analyses that the measuring the activity of social entrepreneurship is integral part of developing and managing SE in every single society. It was evident that social entrepreneurship has remarkable contribution in triple-bottom-line components of community development. In order to measure the activity variety of methods are analyzed alongside and in order to calculate the efficiency of SE new formula is offered.

Conclusion. The development of social entrepreneurship has become widespread throughout the world, including in Uzbekistan. In view of the rapid spread of this new direction of entrepreneurial activity, it became necessary to develop an appropriate methodology for a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of social enterprises. This article will be of interest to undergraduates, graduate students, entrepreneurs and researchers in the field of social entrepreneurship.

Keywords: social entrepreneurship; social and financial value; social and economic efficiency, social project, social benefit, measuring social effect;

Introduction. The social sphere is a complex of both public and private institutions whose activities are aimed at sustainable socio-economic development of the regions, maintaining and improving the quality of life of the population. Branches of the social sphere are called upon to meet

the material, spiritual, educational, medical, cultural and social needs of the population. The most important social category that characterizes the general level of well-being, as well as the degree of satisfaction of human needs, is the quality of life.

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